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A generalized explicit solution applying the residue theorem

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Abstract

We present a generalized explicit solution for the improper integral of a rational function whose denominator is a polynomial of even degree. To this end, we employ some concepts from Complex Analysis, with an emphasis on the Residue Theorem.

keywords: complex analysis, improper integral, residue theorem

The most updated version of this white paper is available at
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13652949>

Introduction

1. This article primarily relies on references [1, 2].
2. In Differential Calculus, calculating improper real integrals is a common practice. When the function to be integrated is rational, the problem becomes particularly interesting.
3. Often, when working with improper real integrals, we can extend the domain of integration to the complex plane, creating a closed curve that includes the real axis and other regions of the complex plane.

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4. The Residue Theorem allows these integrals along closed curves to be calculated by summing the residues of the functions at their isolated singularities within the contour. In this way, we can apply the Residue Theorem to this closed contour (the curve), simplifying the original improper real integral.

Preliminaries

5. Every non-zero complex number z has a polar representation given by $z = r(\cos \theta + i \operatorname{sen} \theta)$, where $r = |z|$ and θ is the argument of z .
6. By Euler's formula, $e^{i\theta} = \cos \theta + i \operatorname{sen} \theta$, this complex number z can be represented as $z = r e^{i\theta}$.
7. Let w be a complex number. We denote the argument of w by $\operatorname{Arg}(w)$.
8. Given a complex number w and a positive integer n , we say that $z \in \mathbb{C}$ is an n th root of w if $z^n = w$.
9. **Theorem A.** Let n be a fixed positive integer. Every non-zero complex number w has exactly n distinct complex n th roots

$$\sqrt[n]{|w|} \left[\cos \left(\frac{\operatorname{Arg}(w) + 2k\pi}{n} \right) + i \operatorname{sen} \left(\frac{\operatorname{Arg}(w) + 2k\pi}{n} \right) \right],$$

where $k = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$.

10. The n distinct complex n th roots of a non-zero complex number w can be written as:

$$\sqrt[n]{|w|} e^{i \left(\frac{\operatorname{Arg}(w) + 2k\pi}{n} \right)}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

11. Let f be an analytic function on the open disk centered at z_0 with radius ρ , except at z_0 , i.e., f is analytic on $B^*(z_0, \rho)$. The residue of f at z_0 is defined by

$$\operatorname{Res}(f, z_0) = \lim_{z \rightarrow z_0} (z - z_0) f(z).$$

12. **Residue Theorem.** Let $U \subset \mathbb{C}$ be an open subset and f an analytic function on U except at a finite number of points z_1, \dots, z_k . For every piecewise smooth curve γ in $U \setminus \{z_1, \dots, z_k\}$, we have

$$\int_{\gamma} f(z) dz = 2\pi i \sum_{j=1}^k \text{Res}(f, z_k).$$

A Generalized Explicit Solution

13. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let us consider the complex function

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{\sum_{\ell=0}^{2n} z^{\ell}}.$$

14. Rewriting the function,

$$\begin{aligned} f(z) &= \frac{(z-1)}{(z-1) \sum_{\ell=0}^{2n} z^{\ell}} \\ &= \frac{(z-1)}{z^{2n+1} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

15. Using (6),

$$z^{2n+1} = 1 = e^{2k\pi i}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, 2n.$$

16. From Theorem A presented in (9), the $2n+1$ roots of $z^{2n+1} = 1$ are

$$a_k = e^{\left(\frac{2k\pi i}{2n+1}\right)}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, 2n.$$

17. Thus,

$$a_0 = 1, \quad a_k = e^{\beta_k i},$$

with $\beta_k = \frac{2k\pi i}{2n+1}$, $k = 1, \dots, 2n$.

18. Using (5)–(6),

$$\begin{aligned} a_q &= \cos \beta_q + i \text{sen } \beta_q, \\ a_{-q} &= \cos \beta_q - i \text{sen } \beta_q, \end{aligned}$$

where $q = 1, \dots, n$.

19. Hence, $a_{-q} = \overline{a_q}$, $q = 1, \dots, n$.

20. Consequently, from (5)–(19), we have

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{\prod_{q=1}^n (z - a_q)(z - a_{-q})}.$$

21. Notice that f is a rational function, and its denominator has no real zeros, i.e., f has no real poles.

22. **Theorem. (Main Result)** For $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sum_{\ell=0}^{2n} x^\ell} dx = \pi \sum_{q=1}^n \frac{1}{\operatorname{sen} \beta_q \cdot \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq q}}^n (a_q - a_j)(a_q - a_{-j})},$$

where $\beta_q = \frac{2q\pi i}{2n+1}$, $q = 1, \dots, n$ and a_1, \dots, a_n are the poles of the integrand function in the upper complex half-plane $M = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : \operatorname{Im} z > 0\}$.

23. We begin the proof by noting that from the rational function we have in the integrand, $f(x) = \frac{1}{\sum_{\ell=0}^{2n} x^\ell}$, we can consider the complex function defined in (13).

24. Thus,

$$\lim_{|z| \rightarrow +\infty} |z^{2n} \cdot f(z)| = P \in \mathbb{R}.$$

25. By the definition of the limit, there exist $Q > 0$ and $S > 0$ such that

$$|z| < S \Rightarrow |f(z)| < \frac{Q}{|z|^{2n}}.$$

26. Consequently, the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) dx$ exists and

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) dx = \lim_{R \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{-R}^R f(x) dx.$$

27. $z = a_q$ and $z = a_{-q}$, $q = 1, \dots, n$ are all the (simple) poles of f .

28. Let $B(0, R)$ be the open disk centered at the origin with radius $R > S$.
29. From (25), $a_q, a_{-q} \in B(0, R)$ for all $q = 1, \dots, n$.
30. The poles $a_q = \cos \beta_q + i \operatorname{sen} \beta_q$, $q = 1, \dots, n$ belong to the upper part of $B(0, R)$.
31. We take the path $C = \gamma_R + C_R$, where

$$\gamma_R(t) = t, \quad -R \leq t \leq R,$$

$$C_R(t) = Re^{it}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq \pi.$$

32. By the Residue Theorem presented in (12), we have

$$\int_C f(z) dz = 2\pi i \sum_{q=1}^n \operatorname{Res}(f, a_q).$$

33. Using (11) and (20),

$$\begin{aligned} \int_C f(z) dz &= 2\pi i \sum_{q=1}^n \lim_{z \rightarrow a_q} (z - a_q) f(z) \\ &= 2\pi i \sum_{q=1}^n \lim_{z \rightarrow a_q} (z - a_q) \frac{1}{\prod_{j=1}^n (z - a_j)(z - a_{-j})}. \end{aligned}$$

34. Calculating the limit, we obtain

$$\int_C f(z) dz = 2\pi i \sum_{q=1}^n \frac{1}{(a_q - a_{-q}) \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq q}}^n (a_q - a_j)(a_q - a_{-j})}.$$

35. From (18)–(19),

$$\int_C f(z) dz = \pi \sum_{q=1}^n \frac{1}{\operatorname{sen} \beta_q \cdot \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq q}}^n (a_q - a_j)(a_q - a_{-j})}.$$

36. Using (25) and (31), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{C_R} f(z) dz \right| &\leq \int_{C_R} |f(z)| |dz| \\ &\leq \frac{Q}{R^{2n}} \int_{C_R} |dz| \\ &\leq \frac{Q\pi}{R^{2n}}. \end{aligned}$$

37. Hence,

$$\lim_{R \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{C_R} f(z) dz = 0.$$

38. Again, from (31),

$$\int_C f(z) dz = \int_{\gamma_R} f(z) dz + \int_{C_R} f(z) dz.$$

39. Thus,

$$\int_{-R}^R f(x) dx = \int_{\gamma_R} f(z) dz = \int_C f(z) dz - \int_{C_R} f(z) dz.$$

40. Taking the limit as $R \rightarrow +\infty$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) dx = \lim_{R \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{-R}^R f(x) dx = \int_C f(z) dz.$$

41. Therefore, from (35), for $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sum_{\ell=0}^{2n} x^\ell} dx = \pi \sum_{q=1}^n \frac{1}{\operatorname{sen} \beta_q \cdot \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq q}}^n (a_q - a_j)(a_q - a_{-j})}.$$

□

Final Remarks

42. This article presented a generalized explicit solution for the improper integral of a rational function whose denominator is a polynomial of even degree, using the Residue Theorem. By applying fundamental concepts from Complex Analysis, it was possible to simplify and solve the problem, contributing to the study of improper integrals and to the understanding of the interactions between rational functions and their complex poles.

43. The developed method can be applied to various problems involving improper integrals of rational functions. Moreover, the application of the Residue Theorem in different contexts may inspire future research in areas where complex integration plays a significant role.

Open Invitation

*Review, add content to, and co-author this white paper [3,4].
Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Supplementary Files

[5]

How to Cite this White Paper

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Acknowledgements

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Agreement

All authors are in agreement with the guidelines presented in [4].

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